

COGNITIVE BASIS OF IMAGERY IN THE LITERARY TEXTS

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Abstract:

This article examines the concept of imagery in English-language literary texts through the prism of cognitive linguistics. Drawing on the work of Lakoff, Turner, Stockwell, and Freeman, the study examines how imagery functions not only as a stylistic device, but also as a fundamental mechanism of human cognition and perception. The article highlights the existing gaps in this field, including the problems of multimodality and individual experience of interpreting images, and concludes that imagery plays a key role in shaping the reader's understanding of literary discourse.

Keywords:

Imagery, cognitive linguistics, metaphor, English texts, blending, conceptualization.

Introduction

The relevance of this study lies in the key role of imagery in English-language texts of the modern world, and today imagery performs not only the function of creating an image in literary works, but also plays a significant role in conceptual representation within the framework of cognitive linguistics. Numerous studies on this topic have been conducted by prominent linguists, including George Lakoff and Mark Johnson, Mark Turner and Gilles Fauconnier, Andreas Musolff, as well as Ilya R. Galperin and others. Their works introduced significant theoretical concepts related to imagery and cognition, identified key issues concerning the role of emotions in shaping imagery, and highlighted the influence of cultural factors on cognitive processes. Nevertheless, linguists have encountered a number of problems while researching this topic, for example, the problem of subjectivity, how to prove that a metaphor is a mechanism of thinking, and not just a beautiful turn of speech. Or, for example, contextual variability, that a metaphor can have different emotional connotations depending on the context.

Literature review

The concept of "imagery" has been explored within various academic disciplines, such as philosophy, literary studies, linguistics, cognitive science, cultural studies, as well as in linguistic subfields including pragmatics, semantics, and stylistics. As a result, the study of imagery has developed into a multifaceted research area characterized by a wide range of theoretical approaches and scholarly perspectives. The linguistic approach and the literary approach are the two primary categories into which the research can be broadly classified. The linguistic approach looks at imagery not just as a stylistic device but as a cognitive and semantic phenomenon. Metaphor is regarded by academics like George Lakoff and Mark Turner as a basic mechanism of human thought. Lakoff showed how metaphor shapes how people perceive and comprehend reality in his seminal work *Metaphors We Live By* [1980]. In *The Literary Mind: The Origins of Thought and Language* [1996], Turner expanded on this concept using the theory of conceptual blending. The literary approach emphasises the reader-text interaction as well as the aesthetic role of imagery in literary texts. For instance, textual imagery relies on the reader's focus on the "figure" [a vivid image] and the "background" [context], according to Peter Stockwell in *Texture: A Cognitive Aesthetics of Reading* [2009]. In books like *The Poem as a Complex System: Integrated Cognitive Poetics* [2020], Margaret Freeman similarly examines

poetry as a cognitive system, contending that poetic imagery enables the expression of emotional experiences through verbal images that readers perceive as nearly physical sensations. Despite the deep theoretical study of the mechanisms of imagination in cognitive linguistics, the question of the practical functioning of images in the modern environment remains open. Linguists have described in detail the processes of understanding metaphors, but such gaps as the mechanisms of multimodality [the interaction of text with video and memes], the influence of individual experience on personal perception of an image, as well as the difficulties of artificial intelligence in recognizing "living" metaphors, which neural networks often interpret literally, remain undisclosed.

Discussion

The word "imagery" comes from the Old French "imagerie", which means figure. This concept allows the reader to draw a beautiful picture and imagine the characters, setting, emotions and situations in the narrative. Moreover, study of the cognitive foundations of imagery in literature has evolved from the classical definition of Aristotle, who emphasized that a metaphor is only "the transfer of a name from a genus to a species by analogy," to the modern cognitive theory of George Lakoff, who argues that "the essence of a metaphor is understanding and experiencing the essence of one species in terms of the essence of another" *Metaphors We Live By* [1980]. Peter Stockwell defines imagery as the dynamic distribution of attention between "figure" and "background" within the reader's cognitive perception of a text [Texture: A Cognitive Aesthetics of Reading, 2009]. In this interpretation, imagery emerges through the interaction between linguistic elements and the cognitive processes involved in reading. A more philosophical understanding of imagery is proposed by José Ortega y Gasset, who describes metaphor as one of the most powerful creative capacities of the human mind: "*The metaphor is perhaps one of man's most fruitful potentialities. Its efficacy verges on magic, and it seems a tool for creation which God forgot inside one of His creatures when He made him.*" [The Dehumanization of Art and Other Essays, 1925]. This perspective emphasizes the creative and almost transformative power of metaphor in shaping human thought and perception.

A more practical definition is provided by Lindy Miller, who explains that imagery refers to the mental images created through the language used by the author. According to Miller, imagery can be understood as the "pictures" that writers create through descriptive language. However, these images are not limited to visual perception and may also involve other sensory experiences [Imagery and Literary Language, 2013]. She further notes that such images may include sensory impressions such as sight, sound, touch, taste, and smell.

- ❖ Visual – to relate to what we see;
- ❖ Auditory – to relate to what we hear;
- ❖ Tactile – related to what we can feel or touch;
- ❖ Olfactory - with what we smell; or
- ❖ Gustatory – related to the sensation of taste and texture in the mouth.

Additionally, some scholars point out that imagery is created by different image-bearing stylistic devices – metaphor, simile, antonomasia, etc. [Kukhareenko, 1998; Arnold, 1999]. Others argue that imagery at the level of the text to the use of figurative means is not limited. The function of images in literature is to create a realistic graphical representation of a scene, taste, smell, touch, fragrance, movement, or emotion. A writer uses images to demonstrate how impressively he/she can convey sensory information to readers, activating their senses so that

the details of any description are understandable. This, in turn, helps to develop the imagination of readers and imagine the characters and scenes in a literary work. In addition to helping readers to clearly perceive information, images created using figurative language such as metaphors, comparisons, onomatopoeia, personifications, etc., serve as decorations for literary works.

Conclusion

In conclusion, imagery is a fundamental mechanism of both literary creativity and cognitive perception of reality, performing both aesthetic and mental functions. Modern study in the field of cognitive linguistics proves that figurative means of language – metaphor, simile, personification, onomatopoeia – not only decorate the text, but form the very perception of reality by the reader. Nevertheless, a number of issues, in particular the mechanisms of multimodality and the influence of individual experience on the interpretation of images, remain open for further research.

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